

**ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ БАНКОВСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ ВО
ФРАНЦУЗСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ И ЕЕ СОВРЕМЕННОЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ
FORMATION OF BANKING TERMINOLOGY IN FRENCH
LANGUAGE AND ITS MODERN APPLICATION**

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Аннотация. Данная статья рассматривает появление терминов в банковской, финансовой и экономической деятельности на первоначальном этапе, их становление и развитие в связи с интеграцией и обменом знаниями между странами в средневековый период, а также их использование в современном банковском секторе государств, в частности Франции. Целью данной статьи является демонстрация и описание исторического аспекта как главного фактора, влияющего на трансформацию имеющихся и заимствование новых иностранных слов, используемых в представленной профессиональной деятельности. В данной работе вниманию предложены основные термины банковской деятельности, не требующих глубоких знаний в этой области, а также занимающих последнее время важное место в повседневной жизни людей, ввиду роста интереса общественности и увеличения влияния экономического развития на уровень и качество жизни населения.

Ключевые слова: термин, банковская деятельность, заимствованные слова, функциональность, денежные операции, французский язык

Summary. This article views the emergence of terms in banking, financial and economic activities at the initial stage, their formation and development in connection with the integration and exchange of knowledge between countries in the medieval period, as well as their use in the modern banking sector of countries, in particular France. The purpose of this article is to demonstrate and describe the historical aspect as the main factor influencing the transformation of existing and borrowing of new foreign words used in the presented professional activity. In this paper, attention is paid to the main terms of banking that do not require deep knowledge in this area, and also occupy an important place in the daily life of people in recent years, due to the growing public interest and the increasing impact of economic development on the level and quality of life of the population.

Keywords: term, banking, derived words, functionality, cash transactions, French language

It should be noted that the term is a word or expression that has a precise meaning in some uses or is peculiar to a science, art, profession, or subject [Merriam Webster`s Dictionary]. In other words, it has its own specifics, which is that terms are created to name objects or phenomena that are meaningful only in the zone of one or another professional sphere, which is based on its own significant concepts and sub-concepts. Only those events and objects are named, to which human activity is directed, and an important role here is played by the final functional design of the indicated object itself. In our case, the taking by the bank functions peculiar to it: keeping money, accumulating money funds, lending, implementing of cash settlements and the function that appears later than others - the right to issue money.

In medieval Europe, many precious coins of various minting were in circulation. To protect themselves from counterfeit coins, merchants kept real money in the counters. In return, they received bills (*récépissés*) - future promissory notes that gave the right to get real money [3,p.128]. Actually, there

are different ways of forming terms in French, the most popular in banking are borrowing and changing the basic meaning of the words. Let look through some of them[1,p.120]:

acompte - this term meant prepayment, word was taken from Italian where financing and banking had already been more developed;

banque - is the main term for banking, it goes back to the Italian word *banca* (1458), which was used in Italy in the XIV century to indicate the counter of the money changer. As a result of the expansion of the meaning, in the 15th century the term began to define a credit institution, as well. However, in France, as a financial term, the word *banque* started to spread later.

billet - "banknote" as a financial term begins to be used in the phrase *billet de banque*, but initially the word *bilette* was used, which meant "receipt";

caisse - this word originally meant "box for transportation", but then it gets the meaning of "cash desk for payment transactions" in financial activities;

credit - in old French the term meant "trust" and began to be used in such expressions as *à crédit, lettres de credit*. Later derived terms arise from *crédit – créditteur and discredit*;

débit - "debit", its primary source was the Latin language, from which the word *debitum* was borrowed with the meaning of "debt";

tarifer - the term "set prices" originated as a derivative of the word *tarif*, which appeared in French due to borrowing the word *tariffa* from Italian.

So, after a long period of transforming, spreading and adapting to the local societies, the banking terminology obtained a modern form, which is used today in French-language countries and organizations. Thus, the main ways of forming the banking terminology of the French language at the first stage of its formation were demonstrated briefly.

Today, banking is playing an increasingly important role in the life of society, in the world economy, in international economic relations, therefore, the analysis of trends in the development of banking terminology is of theoretical and practical importance. Several French banks and insurance companies such as BNP Paribas, Société Générale, Axa occupy an important place in the global banking sector [6,p.81]. They are one of the largest companies with the largest number of workers and employees, so that France can deservedly be considered as the leader in the world financial market and it becomes impossible to ignore its presence. While today banks are an integral part of the life of a modern person, respectively, banking terminology interacts with the general literary language, thereby influencing it.

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